

Pragmatic Study and Analyzing of the American President Trump's Calling Coronavirus "Chinese Virus" and its Moral and Material Effects

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Abstract. *As a matter of fact, pragmatics which is an important linguistic field plays a vital role in communication and interpretation of the speaker's utterance leading to positive or negative results.*

Pragmatics has witnessed many theoretical principles and development since it was founded in the last century. It works side by side with the other different fields like sociology, politics, religion. etc., to give a clear and integrated interpretation of what is said in the communication process.

This paper aims at analyzing the American president Trump's calling "Coronavirus China Virus" and why he said that, but he was criticized by many characters and this led him to defend himself in many occasions.

Trump's calling "Coronavirus China Virus" for racial, political ethno- genic, economic and ideological reasons and to be away from any blaming and responsibility.

Finally, he defended himself why he said that "Coronavirus China Virus" using so many hedge ways.

Key words: *coronavirus, China Virus, sociology, politics, religion racial, political ethno - genic, economic and ideological states.*

Section (One)

1.1. The Problem

This study focuses on the pragmatic components and how and why some people exploit them for their own aims in many fields of language as in politics, social media, propaganda, economics. etc. by telling lie or falsification as in Trump talking of "Coronavirus Chinese Virus".

People can use many pragmatic components like "speech acts" based on (*Austin's most well-known work: 1983*) how to do things with words. Speech acts include three parts:

1. *Locutionary act* (what is said): the basic act of speech.

Example: "I will go to Baghdad" is a statement whereby go means a literal going and so on.

2. *Illocutionary act* (the intention of speech) indicates the speaker's intention, via, producing an utterance.

Example: "I am here now" may be taken as a warning or an apology.

3. *Perlocutionary act* (effect of speech): is the effect of an utterance may have an effect on the addressee like order, request...etc.

Example: Leave now or I will call the police.

Or they can use "implicature which is meant by the speaker yet is not a part of what is explicitly" said, (*Grice:1975*).

Example: A: Will Ali attend the meeting?

B: His car is broken down.

By the two examples above the B' answer does n't include the explicit answer to A's question, or they can use deixis which "is a technical term (from Greek) for one of the basic things we do with utterances. It means pointing, via, language, (*Yule:1996*), such as me, here, that, today....etc.

Also, they can use presupposition due to (*Stalnaker: 1972;1974*), speakers' presupposition or pragmatic presupposition. The presuppositions is associated with specific triggers are said to be conventional or semantic. In fact, this terminological distinction is of theoretical importance:some theorists regard it as an open question whether there are any purely conventional presuppositions.

Example: Jack married Smith's sister. It is supposed that Jack has a sister.

People can do more of pragmatic components to justify and express their speech even they are not logic or incorrect as in Trump's talking about "Coronavirus China Virus". It is clear that pragmatics is one of the most linguistic devises to facilitate the communication between different areas. Sometimes, people may violate pragmatic principles like telling a lie or falsify to express their own view points to achieve their own aims for political, racial. economical ...etc reasons. It is surely these people will be criticized by the others.

1.2. The Aims of this Study

This Paper aims at analyzing Trump's talking of "Coronavirus Chinese Virus" depending on:

1. Defining pragmatics and explaining how people can express what they want to say depending on their mutual knowledge and the meaning in context beyond the literal meaning of the words.
2. Showing how people can exploit or violate the pragmatic principles especially Gricean cooperative maxims i.e. (*quantity, quality, relevance, manner*) to achieve their own purposes like political, economic, religious, humorous and racist ones.
3. Showing how we can analyze the peoples' speech or criticize it.

1.3. The Hypotheses

This paper can be hypothesized that:

1. Trump's talking about "Coronavirus China Virus" as a pragmatic phenomenon which is considered as a dependent variable effect depending on an independent variable cause, that is - the onset of Coronavirus disease.
2. Pragmatic principles can be violated by some people specially the important people to show the power.
3. Trump's talking is related to an ideology in language use by his expressing his ideas, attitudes and prejudices.
4. Hedges and excuses were used by Trump to justify his description of his "Coronavirus China Virus".
5. The pragmatic importance in communication can be either positive or negative.
6. Trump's talking may lead to political, racial. social and economic problems between the *USA* and *China* and may lead to the 3rd world war.

1.4. Paper Questions:

- (a) What are the purposes of this paper?
- (b) Why do we study Trump's talking of "Coronavirus China Virus" pragmatically?
- (c) Why did Trump violate the pragmatic principles in his mentioned claim?

(d) How did Trump try to avoid the criticism and rejection by the others when he described "Coronavirus China Virus"?

1.5. The Study of Methodology in this Paper?

This paper depends mainly on the pragmatic principles and how they can be violated as in Trump's talking about "Coronavirus China Virus" depending on his opinions and how it was analyzed, criticized and rejected by so many people and international organizations like the healthy, social, and humanitarian ones. Trump's talking may lead to the 3rd world war if the matters develop dangerously.

1.6. The Procedures

1. Explaining the concepts of pragmatics and ideology of language use and how they are used in Trump's talking.

2. Treating pragmatic principles and how they can be violated as in Trump's talking.

1.7. Data Collection and Models

1. The data of this paper is a case study on method Trump's talking and it depends on many approaches, theories and techniques based on references of famous linguists' efforts about pragmatic, sociolinguistic principles, language ideologies of some linguists like Verschueren, Lakoff, Huang, Levinson, Searle and others, several essays, articles and some emails. Also, this paper analysis Trump's talking based on the ethical issues like racism, moral and humanitarian issues.

2. Analysing the data of this paper depends on the pragmatic, political, racial, social and economic sides.

3. As for model this paper is classified as a qualitative study depending on information taken from media mentioned Trump's talking and conferences. Trump tries to impose his saying as a universal fact and to make it as a sense of reality by using some sort of pretexts and hedges.

4. The model of this paper is descriptive and ethno-genic related to Trump's talking.

1.8. The Importance of this Paper

Generally, sciences among them linguistics are able to exhibit and explain the world problems, i.e., moral and material ones and this paper explains:

(a) The political, social and psychological and religious problems in Trump's talking of "Coronavirus Chinese Virus" and how we predict its effects.

(b) The criticism and rejection against Trump's talking as a reaction for humanitarian reasons.

(c) Leading to new understanding of the new world as a new start for new and shining future.

(d) Correlating the theoretical and practical sides.

Section (Two)

2.1. Definition of Pragmatics and Language Ideology and How were Used by Trump in his Description of "Coronavirus China Virus".

In fact, there are so many definitions of pragmatics by so many linguists as the following:

(a) Pragmatics is the distinction between what a speaker's words (literally) mean and what the speaker might mean by his words (*Grundy,2002:17*).

(b) Pragmatics is the study of deixis (at least in part) implicature, presupposition, speech acts and aspects of discourse structure (*Levinson:1983:27*).

(c) Pragmatics is the systemic study of meaning by virtue of depending on the use of language, (*Huang:2007:18*).

(d) Pragmatics is the study of relationships between linguistic forms and the uses of those forms (Yule:1996:6).

Whereas, language ideology is a central and strong relationship between language and ideology in pragmatics, sociolinguistics as well as linguistic anthropology. Many pragmaticians explained a new style in the study of ideology in language, via, suitable devices, tools and theories of pragmatics and discourse analysis by Morris, Carnap, Pierce, Levinson, Searle, Verschueren and others. "Language has privileged contribution to the development of ideology, its highly observable nature and the valuable tools developed by linguistic pragmatics for the study of ideology as dynamic process all points to the importance of studying language use or discourse when engaged in ideology research", (Verschueren, 2012: 20).

(Cavanaugh,2019: 17) says, "Language ideologies are this collective order, that is- the beliefs and attitudes that shape speakers' relationships to their own and others' languages, mediating between the social practice of language and the socioeconomic and political structures which within they occur".

Pragmatic rules provide an explicit or implicit set of sociological rules for the functional analysis of language use ideology. Trump uses political sense, values of ideology yet broader, socio-cultural sense with political entailments in his talking of Coronavirus.

Language ideologies are the beliefs, social practice of language depending on race, social class gender or relation between the participants, for example, the "r" sound is not pronounced by the middle social class in the USA. "We learned that language is not just social practice, but it is also and always infused with the political economic and national circumstances", (Cavanaugh,2019:32).The term ideology is traced back to New-Marxist theory to refer to political, economic, philosophical and conceptual system overtly or covertly.

"People may behave or say vague notions of ideology or may follow falsification or verification. Linguistic language ideologies are sets of beliefs about language articulated by users as a rationalization or justification of perceived language structure and use", (Kathryn,1994: 54). Ideology can be seen by some theorists as behavioral, pre reflective or structural signifying practices in lived relation unconsciously and it creates power in other guises and moments.

Trump applied most of the pragmatic principles and ideologies a above in his calling that coronavirus is Chinese Virus. He used the pragmatic components like *speech act* as in making a statement claiming that the Coronavirus is China virus and he used *the implicature* burdening China the responsibility of Coronavirus spreading in a racist and humorous way. Also, he used *the ideology* as he based his talk on his own beliefs and attitudes about what is going on at the hard period of suffering from coronavirus which became epidemic disease forming an international disaster.

2.2. Pragmatic Functions and Guide Lines in Trump's Talking of "Coronavirus as China Virus".

For months, the president Trump has neglected the severity of the epidemic disease of Coronavirus in his policies and treatments, but he was blaming the others specially the Chinese government after the disease became uncontrolled.

On (March, 18,2020) Trump insists on using a racist name of *China Virus* to describe Coronavirus as he intends something beyond his literal words. Trump increases the fear for American people from the foreigners. Also, Trump takes to twitter about Coronavirus, but he insists on naming it the China Virus instead of saying its scientific name "Covid-19".

"I always treated the *China Virus* very seriously and I have done a very good job from the beginning including my very early decision to close the borders from China-against the wishes of almost all. Many lives were saved, (18,March,2020),Trump uses the racist expression deliberately means that he was confused.

Trump's talking is antagonizing *China* at the worst time causes an international crisis as in his saying "that he was pushing back on conspiracy theory-that did, in fact, started in *China* which is blaming the *U.S.* military for spreading the disease, *China* was putting out information, which was false, that

our military gave this to them that was false and rather than having an argument, I had to call it where it did come from, it is very accurate term".

Trump himself sent out a tweet on Monday (17, March, 2020) naming Covid-19 the *Chinese virus* and later he repeated it on Wednesday when he started a new conference.

What he said, in fact, in this conference was an intentional provocation and racism when he used the term yellow peril indicating to *China*, of course this style belongs to implicature (the hidden intention), as Trump was indicating the *Chinese people or government* by his expression the "yellow peril".

Trump uses in his speech so many pragmatic principles in his description of the Covid-19 like the speech acts in his statements with their constatives phrases as in naming Covid-19 "*Chinese Virus*" to justify that it came from China to put himself a way from the criticism.

In addition, he uses implicit phrases as in "I always treated the *Chinese Virus* very seriously and I have done a very good job from the beginning when I used *China Virus* phrase" implicating a sense to burden China the responsibility of coronavirus and he uses the presupposition. Trump's talking is supposed that coronavirus appeared and spread in *China* at first.

In relation to politeness, Trump committed a face-threatening act strategy in his description coronavirus as *Chinese Virus* when he tried to blame China and distort its reputation among the other nations in that expression. According to *Brown and Levinson(1987:18)*, face-threatening acts may threaten either the speaker's face or the hearer's face, and they may threaten either positive face or negative face. A face-threatening act (FTA) can be defined as an act which challenges the face wants of speakers or hearers.

FTAs Threatening the Hearer's Face

Positive Face

FTAs threatening the hearer's self-image include **(i)** expressions negatively evaluating the hearer's positive face, e.g. disapproval, criticism, complaints, accusations, contradictions, disagreements etc., as well as **(ii)** expressions which show that the speaker does not care about H's positive face, e.g. expressions of violent emotions, taboo topics, bad news, emotional topics, interruptions etc.

Example: I think your letter was not concise enough.

Criticism: In this example the hearer's positive face has been threatened because s/he is blamed for having done something badly, i.e. his/her self-image is negatively evaluated.

Negative Face

FTAs reducing the hearer's personal freedom include **(i)** acts predicating a future act of the hearer, e.g. orders/requests, suggestions/advice, reminding, threats/warnings/dares, **(ii)** acts predicating a future act of the speaker towards the hearer, e.g. offers/promises, and **(iii)** acts expressing a desire of the speaker towards the hearer or his/her goods, e.g. compliments, expressions of emotions.

Examples: Close the door. (order)

Be careful. (warning)

If you leave early, I will fire you. (dare)

The addressee might be embarrassed for or fear the speaker as: disrespect, mention of topics which are inappropriate in general or in the context.

Example: I will call him a stupid boy.

The speaker increases the possibility that a face-threatening act will occur. This situation is created when a topic is brought up by the speaker that is a sensitive societal subject as: topics that relate to politics, race, religion and society.

Sometimes the white people call the black people nigger or slaves, also the white people call the American-Asians yellow race.

The speaker says that he is distinguished from the positive face wants of the hearer. This state is often expressed in clear non-cooperative behavior.

The speaker may use an offensive or embarrassing way and this may occur accidentally or intentionally. Generally, this refers to the misuse of address terms in relation to status, gender, nationality or age.

Example: Addressing a young woman as "ma'am" instead of "miss."

Trump uses topics that relate to politics, race, religion in his negative threatening against China by his racial expression *Chinese Virus*.

2.3. Definition of Cognitive Pragmatics and How it was Used in Trump's Talking of China Virus.

"Cognitive pragmatics can be broadly defined as encompassing the study of the cognitive principles and processes involved in the construal of meaning in context", (*Schmidt, 2012:99*). Speakers often try to compose what they say in a way to convey their message easily to the hearers relying on hearers' knowledge by adding conceptual and emotive components beyond the literal meaning of utterance. Pragmatics should label such cognitive issues anyway, philosophy of language, psycholinguistics and topical linguistics.

Example: A: Will it rain?

B: The clouds are scattered.

Here the B's reply is not by yes or no, but by indirect way depending on the mutual knowledge between the speaker and the hearer that scattered clouds will not lead to rain.

The psychology of pragmatics is what are the actual cognitive processes taking place during online construal meaning –in-context on the bases of encoded messages, "ibid". Cognitive pragmatics depends on the mental states of the participants in a conversation depending on cooperation, share and communicative intention.

The cooperative principles due to (Grice, 1975:45) are justified by reasoning forming an utterance as the following:

(a) *Quantity:* is a contribution which should be as informative as is required.

Example: S: What is your name?

H: My name is Ali.

(b) *Quality:* is saying the truth.

Example: The earth move around the sun.

(c) *Relevance:* is the relation between the speaker's question and hearer's answer.

Example: S: Where is the book?

H: The weather is nice.

(d) *Manner:* the utterance should be order, logic and not obscure.

Example: I started my car, warmed it and then set out to my work.

Share can form non-standard messages like irony, deceit, figurative of speech which do not obey any one of the cooperative maxims:

1. Flouting of quantity maxim.

Example: A: Well, how do I look ?

B: Your shoes are nice, (*Cutting, 2002:24*).

2. Flouting of quality maxim.

Example: I could eat a camel.

3. Flouting of relation maxim.

Example: A: So what do you think of mark?

B: His flat mate is a wonderful cook., (*Cutting 2002:24*).

4. Flouting of manner maxim

Example: A: What do you need?

B: I need that funny white stuff for somebody.

B's speech is ambiguous. (*Cutting,2002:25*).

Finally, communicative intention can present the unique features of recursion of humans, but Trump violated the quality principle of Grice's maxims which imposes to say the truth when he described "Coronavirus *Chinese Virus*" and he repeats it many times, but the virus has no country or nationality as scientists say.

In his speech, Trump used the cognitive pragmatics when he tried to deceive people by using the racist phrase like *China Virus*, yellow peril to increase the discrimination towards Asian- Americans malice, distancing himself from the criticism and he exploited it as a propaganda for his next election campaign. He depends upon his concepts of the out world that most people are suffering from the wide spreading of coronavirus as well as the psychological effects resulting from that virus on people all over the world in his description of coronavirus as *China Virus*.

2.4. Definition of Sociopragmatics and How it was Used in Trump's Talking

"Sociopragmatics is a general cognitive, social and cultural perspective on phenomena in behavior",(*Verschuerenl,1999:123*).Sociopragmatics concerns with the general states of the communication language. Sociopragmatics allows speakers to exploit more general norms to create particular meanings. The term Sociopragmatics was coined by the linguist Leech in 1966 to study the ways by which pragmatic meaning reflects condition in language use",(*Culpeper, 1988:76*).

Sociopragmatics focuses mainly on the social principles of speaking held by individuals of a speech community as normal behavior.

Example: when an employment asks his/her boss.

S:Could I get any bonus, sir?

H:The market is stagnant.

Trump exploited more general norms like his social and political situation to use the utterance *China Virus* to create that particular meaning in his naming coronavirus *Chinese Virus* to restrict this covid-19 to *China*.

3.1. Many Characters and Organizations Criticized Trump's Naming of the Chinese Virus.

Actually, many characters and organizations have criticized Trump's naming of the *Chinese Virus* from their humanitarian viewpoints:

Trump's adviser: "Politics has no place in this crisis".

Bardella (March, 18, 2020): "His arrogant belief in American exceptionalism has often resulted in the scapegoating of other nations".

The president's naming was met with resistance from most administration officials, saying that ethnicity is not the cause of the novel coronavirus.

Michael Ryan, the executive director of The World Health Organization emphasized that viruses know no borders and scolded Trump for his statements regarding the *Chinese Virus*, "here is antagonizing *China* at the absolute worst time. Then is a good chance, however, that Trump is digging in because he is being influenced by the racist ignorance".

Also, democratic lawmakers have the same objections.

Dr. Robert Redfield (8, March, 2023), the director of Federal Centers for Disease Control and Prevention said, "it was absolutely wrong and inappropriate to use this the Chinese coronavirus".

China has strongly objected to the use of the term *Chinese Virus* calling that description as a despicable practice.

The characters above implied the relation between pragmatic and literary criticism which is concerned mainly with the ethical effect of the text upon the audience socially and psychologically, to establish a moral impact with knowledge of truth and goodness.

By what mentioned above it is clear that the critics above implied the illocutionary (the speaker's intention) which is a kind of speech acts relating to blaming Trump for his description of "*Coronavirus as Chinese Virus*".

3.2, Trump's Hedges and Defenses in His Calling "Coronavirus Chinese Virus".

After, Trump has got many blaming and criticisms, he restored to the hedge style which is a linguistic way adopted by people to be away from criticism by using some phrases like "I think", "as a I know", "someone saidetc. This way was coined by the linguist *Lakoff* in 1972.

Trump mentioned in one conference that "the cause comes from China. It's not racial at all. It comes from *China* that's why I want to be accurate".

Also, Trump said "that he was pushing back in a conspiracy theory –that did, in fact started in China, I had to call it where it came from, it did come from *China*, so I think it's a very accurate term".

Section (Three)

Conclusion

Any viruses or diseases have no borders or nationality around the world. They may appear here or there at any time, therefore, no one can name any virus or disease by any nationality or country.

Experts have warned that limiting to a geographic area will surely hinder the efforts to control it, and Trump's behavior may cause fear from the foreigners and cause the hatred against them and it may lead to the 3rd world war in case of increasing the stress between *America and China*, God forbid.

Trump's Calling coronavirus the *Chinese Virus* may inflame the racial stress and discrimination in Asian-Americans especially when Trump warned from the yellow peril referring to the Chinese people.

Trump's strange behavior may be a good example and lesson for the others to avoid like these racial expressions to make people in all over the world help each other to avoid any disaster, virus, disease or something like that. It was easy to analyze Trump's talking and how he was criticized depending on the pragmatics and its relationships to the other fields like Sociopragmatics, ideology, cognitive pragmatics and psycholinguistics.

Finally, language has a wide range in all walks of life politics, sociology, religion, economics philosophy ---etc. and anyone can exploit this characteristic to achieve his/her own aim.

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